
‘Adolescence’: The Period of Storm and Stress: A Study on Various Developments, Problems and Their Remedies

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ARTICLE DETAILS

Research Paper

Accepted on: 24-02-2025

Published on: 14-03-2025

Keywords:

Development, Adolescence, Storm and Stress, Issues, and Solutions

ABSTRACT

Puberty marks the start of adolescence, a time of major development that lasts until the mid-20s. There is a significant degree of change in all areas of development—biological, cognitive, psychosocial, emotional, etc.—between those two ages. During this time, the teenager enters and then leaves secondary school, finds employment, and experiences changes in personal connections and environments. Teenagers are becoming more and more involved in their personal growth. But even as they experiment, explore, and learn, kids still need help and scaffolding, including settings that increase their chances of success. Healthy teenage development is difficult in a hazardous environment. In the end, the physical, mental, and behavioural changes that take place during adolescence interact with.

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15030242>

INTRODUCTION:

The word "adolescence" comes from the Greek word "adolescere," which means to mature. Boys and girls go from childhood to adulthood throughout adolescence, which includes changes in their mental, emotional, social, and physical development. It is the most formative time of a person's life. Both the physical and mental aspects of life are changing significantly at this point. Adolescence typically occurs between the ages of 12 and 18. This is a time when infancy is recapitulated and later childhood stability is no longer present. This research is descriptive in nature. Through the study, the researcher will draw

attention to the different issues, developments, and solutions that occur during the adolescent stage. G. Stanley Hall's seminal work at the start of this century marked the beginning of the systematic study of adolescence. Some societal myths about adolescence predominated before Hall's research. Despite scientific contradiction and rejection, some of them continue to persist.

1. The first misperception is that teenagers have ungainly bodies. It is quite challenging to pinpoint the source of this widespread misunderstanding regarding teenagers. It might have started because some teenagers are as big as adults.
2. The second myth is that teenagers are disobedient. Although this was a long-held belief, it is not supported by psychological principles. Current research has demonstrated that this belief is untrue, as there is no justification for teenage rebellions if their energy is well directed. The final myth is that teenagers grow up quickly. Development studies have demonstrated that human growth is an ongoing process, and it is accurate to state that less change occurs throughout adolescence than over the same period of years starting at birth.
3. The fourth erroneous belief is that the issues associated with sex maturation concern teenagers. It's the wrong perspective. Although interest in sex is undoubtedly very recent, it varies depending on the nation's socioeconomic and cultural circumstances.

Human development and growth are spiral rather than linear. As a result, we discover a kind of repetition and similarity of traits among the many periods of life. It is frequently seen that elderly people act like youngsters. We also observe a kind of recapitulation and recurrence of the actions taken from infancy in adolescence. Adolescence, like infancy, is a time of excessive restlessness and disruption; in Stanley Hall's words, it is "a period of great stress and strain, storm and strife."

THE IMPORTANCE OF ADOLESCENCE STUDY

1. All educators and parents need to be aware of the characteristics and changes that occur during the childhood-to-adult transition period. To effectively address the issues of adolescents, they must also be aware of the different issues that are accompanied by developmental traits.
2. A nation's ability to advance depends on how well its people resources are utilised. Second, one of the first prerequisites for development is mental wellness. Adolescence is characterised by a variety of issues that impact mental health. The study of adolescence is crucial for preventing, treating, and preserving maladjustment.

3. The study is important because it sheds light on the demands and developmental tasks of adolescents. Teachers and parents can assist teenagers in acclimating to their new roles. Teachers and administrators may create curricula, school regulations, and teaching methods that are appropriate for adolescents by having a thorough grasp of their requirements.
4. A desire to learn more about oneself may motivate someone to research teenage psychology. If the student is in the adolescent stage, this desire is perfectly reasonable and natural. The older person who studies the adolescence has within himself a potential source of insight into issues facing the person of adolescence period - issues that once he had to face. It may also be due to the scholarly interest of the individual.

GOALS OF THE STUDY:

1. The primary goal of this research is to understand the different kinds of adolescent growth.
2. To research the issues that teenagers confront.
3. To research potential solutions to the issues.

METHODOLOGY:

Secondary data forms the basis of this investigation. They are gathered from a variety of publications, including books, journals, and published research. We can better comprehend our teens by looking at their growth and developmental patterns as well as the unique traits of this age group. Let's start by attempting to comprehend the changes that occur in the children's personalities during this time.

(1) PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT AND CHANGES:

Adolescence is characterised by notable physical changes that have a big impact on behaviour.

- i. During this time, the height of nearly all boys and girls' changes. The pubertal growth period, which lasts an average of 15 years and ranges from 13 to 17 years, is linked to height growth.
- ii. One well-known aspect of teenage development is the variations in boy's voice. During adolescence, girls' voices become pleasant while guys' voices become gruff. Adolescent behaviour can occasionally be significantly impacted by a change of voice.

- iii. Physiological changes: The body's internal systems have undergone significant alteration. By the age of eighteen, the brain is fully developed, and all systems, including the respiratory, circulatory, digestive, blood pressure, heart, and pulse rate, reach their full growth.
- iv. Physical activity and ability: During adolescence, the ability to engage in physical activities improves quickly.
- v. Changes in strength speed: According to psychologists who performed tests of muscular strength and physical power as shown by hand grip strengths, there is a significant rise in muscular strength during adolescence.

(2) CHANGES AND DEVELOPMENT OF EMOTION

Adolescence is a time of intense emotional agitation. All emotions, including love, rage, fear, and anxiety, are at their peak during this time. Adolescence is a time when people experience emotional instability and intensity, much like an infant does. The body's strength allows for the greatest amount of motor activity when physical growth and development are at their peak. Adolescence thus offers the highest peak in terms of emotional expression and experiences. He is quite agitated, emotionally disturbed, and touchy at this point. He is excessively temperamental, volatile, and sensitive. Teenagers' emotional expressions are inconsistent. They experience rapid and frequent emotional swings. There are specific signs that indicate emotional problems in teenagers. The instructor can identify these teenagers in his class and offer them one-on-one counselling. Excessive nail biting, thumb sucking, lip biting, nose scratching, hair pulling or twisting, head scratching, face picking, hand touching, learning the face on the hands, leg rocking, etc. are some of the signs. Emotional distress is also indicated by the use of other processes, such as hyperactivity, shyness, hostility, inattention, and withdrawal. Teenagers often exhibit the following emotional patterns:

- i. Love and affection - The emotion of love is very important in adolescents and is related to sexual impulse. The emotion of love and affection develops from the very infancy in the life of the organisms. The adolescent is able to discriminate people with whom he likes to associate and build up an affectionate association. Gillind reports that childhood loves are not sexual in nature but in adolescence love becomes a source of pleasure., the

maturation of sex is the chief source of newness in the lives of adolescents. Most of his conversation centres round the sex and its problems.

- ii. Joy, pleasure and Delight: During adolescence physical condition is one of the sources of joy and pleasure. The first cause of joy is one in which the individual fits, or to which, by virtue of his capabilities and abilities, he is well-adjusted. The second situation which calls forth joy in the adolescent is the release of pen-up energy. The third common cause of happiness in adolescent is the feeling of superiority.
- iii. Worry: It is an imaginary fear. It is caused by a repeated rehearsal of the situation feared. The adolescents have the following type of worriers.

Academic assignments

Inspection and assessment

Issues in school, such as teacher partiality, excessive schoolwork, difficulty focussing, inability to learn, fear of failing, and shortcomings pertaining to their sexual role.

- iv. Concerns at home: Insufficient communication between teenagers and their parents, parental illness, marital difficulties, friends' health, financial difficulties, and personality flaws.
- v. Fear: One significant negative feeling. Fear of things like snakes, dogs, unusual noises, lions, elephants, and social interactions including meeting persons in high positions, senior citizens, being by themselves in a room, reciting in front of the class or speaking from a platform, and meeting people of the other sex.

(3) CHANGES AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE MENTAL SKILLS

Adolescence is the time of greatest mental functioning growth and development. Among the traits of mental development are:

- i. A greater capacity for factual generalisation.
- ii. Improve comprehension skills.
- iii. A better capacity to handle abstraction.
- iv. Memory and imagination development.
- v. Develop your problem-solving skills.

- vi. An improved capacity for interpersonal communication.
- vii. Develop decision-making skills.
- viii. Knowledge of moral principles.

Adolescents develop their ability to reason and look for the how and why of all scientific phenomena. He cultivates a vivid imagination. During this time, poets, writers, artists, philosophers, and inventors were all born. A teenager may start daydreaming if their imagination and unmet needs are not properly channelled. As a result, it is crucial to properly cultivate their imaginative power.

(4) SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT:

Adolescence is the period of increased social relationships and contacts. The adolescents become sensitive to public praise or blame. He ceases to be ego-centric selfish and unsocial. Now he wants to mould his behaviour according to the norms of the society. One important development at this stage is the increased influence of peer group. The peer group or the gang shapes the behaviours of the adolescents. His attitude, interests and moral values are guided by peers. The child's ties with his parents and the family represent another important shift in his social characteristics during adolescence. There is now a desire for autonomy. He desires for the parents and older family members to recognise his personality. You can't treat him like a kid. His parents' advice is not as important to him as the principles and ideas upheld by his peer group. If the parents attempt to force their beliefs and ideals on their teenage offspring, there may even be covert or overt rebellion.

(4) MORAL AND RELIGIOUS DEVELOPMENT

The youngsters learn to behave in accordance with the standards of their culture and society as their civic and social senses grow. The process of moral growth is accelerated during this time by the development of strong feelings. At this age, a person also experiences the effects of religion and religious rituals for the first time. An adolescent attempts to discuss religion and God. He frequently discusses philosophical ideas like the soul, Brahm, the purpose of life, the issue of death, etc.

(5) SEX-INSTINCT GROWTH:

The most powerful influence in an adolescent's life is sex. Teenagers exhibit restless and amorous behaviour at this point due to the sex instinct's activation. They are drawn to people of

the other sex, but they are unsure of how to approach them in a friendly manner. Premature sex indulgence and abrupt restraint of the same can cause various issues in children at this age. Anxiety-neurosis, depression, and phobia can result from suppressing sexual urges.

(6) INTEREST DEVELOPMENT:

They form four categories of interests. (i) Recreational (ii) Social (iii) Individual (iv) Professional

Boys and girls have a wide range of interests during the adolescent stage. Their areas of interest significantly broaden as their intellectual and social development progresses. They discuss problems facing the nation or society from different angles. This is the time when their passion for reading peaks. Novels, adventure stories, and biographies of notable persons are among the books they enjoy reading. Cinema, TV and radio have great impact on interest of adolescents in recent years. They are interested in travelling. They enjoy seeing new things and wish to be somewhat freed from the drab and repetitive home. Adolescents enjoy adventurous pursuits like mountaineering and discovering new locations in addition to travelling. They developed an interest in strengthening their bodies through games and other physical activities after becoming aware of their physical well-being.

ADOLESCENCE PROBLEMS:

Adolescence is a time of transition from childhood that entails a number of changes in development. Hall has described this time as stressful and stormy. Adolescents face numerous contradictory circumstances and adjustment issues that require thorough examination. We will thus consider the causes of these issues and attempt to evaluate the particular needs and expectations of this era.

Adolescent issues were categorised by S.R. Laycock under the following main tasks:

- (i) Adjustment to opposite sex, school, and society.
- (ii) Independence from home
- (iii) Adaptation to a suitable career.
- (iv) Creating a good life philosophy.

(i) *Adjustment at home*: Teenagers demand greater autonomy to go to social events, but their parents forbid them from leaving the house. The second significant issue is that parents have high expectations for their children's success, and when those expectations are not met, there is ongoing conflict between parents and teenagers. These arguments can occasionally have disastrous results. Teenagers may run

away from home and end their lives. Parents and teenagers don't understand each other. Teenagers are treated like children by their parents. They never openly discuss issues with them.

(ii) *School adjustment*: The majority of teenagers struggle to adapt to the strict schedule and curriculum. Teachers lack empathy and are inflexible. Teenagers worry about exams, the pass-fail system, and their parents' goals. The child either develops neuroticism or delinquency when he is unable to adapt to the strict educational system.

(iii.) *Social adjustment*: In a society, adolescents act like adults. They have to pick up etiquette and social conventions. They are made fun of when they don't follow the rules set out by the adults in the community. They are unable to act in accordance with their conscience. Adolescents experience serious mental conflicts as a result of all of them.

(iv) *Adjustment with opposite sex*: A unique sex consciousness characterises the decline of adolescence. His romantic activity is a result of this drive being awakened. The adolescent is attracted to the person of the opposite sex, but he is unsure about how to establish a friendship with them in light of social taboos. As a result, the young spirit suffers greatly from inadequate guidance. A person with a completely misplaced sexual urge is afflicted with a number of psychiatric illnesses. Abnormal sexual activities of the adolescents give rise to melancholia in which he is haunted by a sense of sin, and thinks himself lost beyond redemption.

(iv) *Vocational issue* (fitting into a suitable career):

Uncertainty about their future careers is the biggest issue that teenage boys in India worry about. What will be done after studying is the issue haunting teenagers' thoughts. The fact that thousands of teenagers lack jobs is another negative aspect of the situation. Adolescents revolt because their minds are agitated against the social order. It is also regrettable that the majority of our teenagers do not plan for the future when they study. Once they have exhausted all independent sources of income.

(v) *Idealism V/s Realism*: Teenagers want to contribute to the development of a perfect society. He considers enacting reform and is highly critical of the current situation and events. He searches for some high goals and ideals in an attempt to elevate himself. He also seeks a set of moral principles that he can comprehend and some guiding principles that he can follow. But in this search of idealism he goes away from realism. In the attempt of touching sky from the ground he is deprived of the support which is available from the ground. In fact lack of experience makes him somewhat unrealistic. He tends to accept the impossible when it is not attainable he becomes quite disturbed and unreasonable. Many of the teenagers become troublesome young

people. Some of them grow gloomy and think that anything that stands in the way of their dreams should be destroyed. Some people start to retreat and daydream. They have the potential to develop maladjusted personalities when they start to wander around in their own fantasy, fantasy, and fairy tale world. (vii) The issue of health adjustment: Adequate social adjustment depends heavily on physical health. In terms of their physical appearance, both boys and girls have extremely specific standards. Adolescents who are either overly or underdeveloped struggle greatly with adjustment.

ACTIONS THAT SHOULD BE TAKEN:

It is the duty of all of us, including parents, educators, and other family and community members, to properly address the issues that teenagers encounter. The following actions are considered necessary.

1. Parents, educators, and other family members ought to be properly informed about the psychology of adolescents. Adolescence is an extremely delicate time. Therefore, a thorough analysis of the adolescent's behaviour and personality is necessary. In order to comprehend adolescents, everyone should be aware of their psychology. In order to effectively deal with teenagers, parents, educators, and administrators must be aware of their unique requirements, the changes that occur during their time, the issues they confront, and the best ways to handle them.
2. Adolescence is the period where maximum growth take place. For getting maximum, what one can get with respect to physical and mental growth suitable environment should be provided by the parents and the teachers at home as well as in schools. They must be provided with balanced diet. Their eating habit should be checked up. To utilise his physical energy at this period, some kind of physical activities should be prescribed for adolescent boys and girls. Drill, gymnastic and manual training are of great help in developing physical and motor power of the adolescent. Various kinds of sports and games are to be encouraged among adolescents. All kinds of outdoor activities should be provided to the adolescent boys and girls. The new system of education in our country prescribes physical education and work education for school children to channelize their physical and mental energy. Adolescence should be encouraged to participate in these activities. In schools, adolescents should be given physical and health education and

there should be arrangement for regular medical check-up of the adolescent boys and girls.

3. During adolescence, sex is extremely prevalent. Some sources are in charge of supplying information about sex. Teenagers' mental and physical health suffers as a result of the information they learn from these sources. Due to a lack of appropriate supervision and inaccurate information about sex, many teenagers suffer from a variety of illnesses. Therefore, it is important to start providing sex education to children at a young age. In our country, most of the parents are conservative in their outlook regarding sex problems. The curiosity of sex needs satisfaction. For this purpose, the parents and the teachers should provide adequate information regarding the sex hygiene and physiology, the process of the birth of a baby, the hazards of immature and before marriage intercourse etc in a very frank, scientific, judicious and impersonal manner. Sex education should form an integral part of regular curriculum for the adolescent boys and girls. Various topics of sex education should be included in subjects like science, Home science, Psychology and Sociology etc.
4. According to recent studies in the field of adolescent psychology, the true issue with adolescence is the irrational viewpoints of adults, parents, elders, and teachers. They constantly condemn the teenagers, exert their power, and state what they like and dislike. They fail to recognise the generational divide between themselves and teenagers. The parents and teachers should understand that their peer group's needs come before their own when interacting with them. They constantly work to uphold their position and self-esteem among their peers during the adolescent stage. They consider themselves to be grown individuals now. They should not be given a patient hearing, but their opinions should be respected. They should be allowed the freedom to express themselves and their thoughts should be solicited. They must abstain from actions that harm the student's sense of self. Teachers and parents should cease muttering and uncritically critiquing the behaviour and attitude of the teenagers. Young people need role models more than they need critics. The wants and issues of adolescents must be carefully considered by the elder.
5. The adolescent stage is characterised by excessive emotional vigour, intensity, instability, and immaturity. They are restless and extremely combustible. Therefore, it is imperative that teenagers receive emotional education. Their emotional energies should

be directed towards positive goals and their emotions should be appropriately trained. Teenagers should be allowed to follow their own path and develop their own way of life, but they also need the love, support, and safety of their parents, teachers, and elders. If he is not given adequate security and anxiety-free living conditions, he will be upset. What the teenagers need in terms of their emotional needs must be provided to the parents and instructors.

6. One of the most crucial topics for both boys and girls in their adolescence is individual care and attention. Regarding their unique interests and skills, they differ greatly from one another. Depending on their unique interests, they ought to be given educational opportunities and chances to engage in extracurricular activities.
7. Vocational needs should be met: A child does not give much thought to his future vocation until he is twelve years old, but by the time he is sixteen, he begins to do so. They started to worry about becoming economically independent. As a result, they require appropriate vocational education and guidance. Therefore, it is imperative that teenagers receive practical education that is vocation-based and job-oriented in the modern world. Parents, educators, society, and the government should all work towards this goal.
8. To lessen restlessness, indiscipline, dishonesty, and aimlessness among India's youth, adolescents should be given access to religions and moral instruction. They ought to offer moral and character-building education. Together, parents, educators, social workers, and administrators should create an environment that is conducive to moral behaviour and provide chances for moral practice.
9. Through dance, music, and arts and crafts, adolescents should be given the chance to develop their creative potential. Divergent thought ought to be promoted. Through his interactions and instruction in the classroom, the instructor should set an example for the students. Teenagers should be taught to have a positive outlook on life by their teachers.
10. Creating an environment that supports the healthy development of students' mental faculties is one of the school's key responsibilities. The school ought to offer community service, free discussion forums, and well-stocked libraries. Adolescent needs should be appropriately addressed in the curriculum.

CONCLUSION:

According to the study, adolescence is a time when both boys and girls experience a wide range of demands, issues, and growth. As parents, educators, and other members of the community, we should always be understanding of their issues and make an effort to take into account their psychological requirements. Only then will they be able to conquer the many challenges of puberty if we assist them in finding empathetic solutions to their problems.

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